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**Case study 4:
Netherlands**

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Executive Summary

This is the third case study on legal information provision done in the context of the Openlaws project. It follows the structure and approach of those on the EU and the United Kingdom. It is a case study of the Netherlands' provision of legal information, including commercial, in terms of cases, legislation, regulatory instruments and academic expert analysis.

As with previous case studies, the study involves a review of the existing sources of access to legal information, as shaped by the socio-economic and legal context of the Netherlands. The findings are similarly informed by a series of interviews, desk research, literature review and the insights of a joint Openlaws/LAPSI workshop¹.

The Netherlands has a mature, well-developed service industry, with a long-standing history of powerful professional publishers, and a particularly innovative public sector. The Dutch government was already keen in the mid-1990s to improve public availability of government information online and continues to work today on making this data truly accessible and manageable to the public at large.

Today it pursues open access and open data policies. Gold and green open access is to be the norm for publicly-funded, *scientific* research, including legal research outputs such as articles, books, case comments. Primary legal information is among the many types of government information that is increasingly released as open data (legislation, court decisions, parliamentary records). As a result uptake of open access in legal publishing is gaining pace, albeit that the effect is most notable in academic publishing.

The two largest legal publishers, Wolters Kluwer and SDU, have traditionally enjoyed a competitive advantage over their peers, given their historical ties to the public sector. Several smaller specialized publishers cater to specific target groups: students, legal specialists in a particular field, etc. Fairly new market actors in the Netherlands are legal content integrators, which offer search, access and information management services to the private and public sectors. Indeed, many of the interviewed publishers emphasize that *content* is no longer king in legal publishing, especially where it concerns texts of regulations and court decisions.

¹ The joint LAPSI /Openlaws workshop *Open Legal Data for Europe* took place at the University of Amsterdam. See report: M van Eechoud and O Salamanca, 'Open Legal Data for Europe', Openlaws Workshop Report, Institute for Information Law (IViR), September 2014. LAPSI (*Legal Aspects of Public Sector Information, 2.0*) is a thematic network funded by the European Commission under the *2007-2013 Competitiveness and Innovation Framework Programme*>. See <http://www.ivir.nl/onderzoek/lapsi>.

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1 Context

1.1 Legal System

The Netherlands has a civil law system, influenced, amongst others, by the French Napoleonic Code and German law, in line with other legal systems present in Continental Western Europe. Case law is a key source for understanding the law, especially where statutory norms are of an open character. In practice, it is very relevant to the shaping of subsequent judicial rulings, of law and of policy. Lower courts will follow Supreme Court (with the constitutional task to guard the unity of the law), CJEU and ECHR judgments, applying the usual methods of interpretation for cases that are not clearly addressed by higher courts. Access to court decisions is one important instrument, for both the court themselves (intra-court access) and the general public, to promote the unity of law.

1.2 Public Sector Information: Publicity of Legal Information

The Dutch government has traditionally played an active role in releasing public sector information to its citizens, and saw, very early on, the opportunities that information and communication technologies (*ICT*), notably the internet offer in this respect. In other words, though the constitutional obligation to publish the laws and the ‘copyright-free’ status of laws as per the Dutch Copyright Act duly paved the way for the dissemination of legal information², it was very distinctively the policy undertaken by the Dutch government since the late 1980s that was key to the development. This policy seems to have stripped away to a large extent the need for ‘*free access to law movements*’, and legal information institutes in The Netherlands. In fact, these appear to be rather common law-related phenomena³.

Another important characteristic of the Dutch state that helped ease the process is its unitary system, with a limited amount of rule-making at local and regional level, as well as a centralised judicial system.

However, it is worth noting that the original rationale for unifying and disseminating electronic legal information was efficiency driven. Until the early 1990s, the focus of the Dutch government was more on achieving efficient access to legal information for uses within public administration (law databases, parliamentary records system, etc.) than on

² Article 88 of the Dutch Constitution declares that the ‘publication and entry into force of Acts of Parliament shall be regulated by Act of Parliament. They shall not enter into force before they have been published’. In other words, laws must be published in order to have effect. Article 11 of the Dutch Copyright Act (DCA) also cleared that path further, indirectly incentivizing re-use and stripping legal datasets of a large part of its potential financial worth by asserting that ‘no copyright subsists in laws, decrees or ordinances issued by public authorities, or in judicial or administrative decisions’.

³ See J Bing, ‘Let there be LITE: a brief history of legal information retrieval’, *European Journal of Law and Technology*, Vol. 1, Issue 1, 2010 “Perhaps LIIs have been both most successful and most needed in jurisdictions where there has been a formal control of the publishing of legal sources, for instance by applying Crown Copyright. Partly, the LIIs represent a reaction to a restrictive and protective attitude towards making legal material available to the public.”

informing citizens. The former State printer SDU was privatized, yet remained official printer and commercial exploiter of some legislative material. Kluwer became a major IT database expertise partner. Both remain the key legal publishers to date: SDU retained its traditional role as official printer and from there would venture into electronic (official) publishing, while Kluwer remained a powerful publisher of legal information with expertise (already at the time) in the provision of electronic access.

From the mid-1990s that the Dutch government started looking more to its own role in providing access to information to meet citizen needs, inspired by the development of the Web. In June 1997, the Dutch Ministry of Interior published a policy paper ('Nota') titled '*Towards the accessibility of public sector information (Naar Toegankelijkheid van Overheidsinformatie)*'. The paper set out a policy framework (*beleidskader*) for making electronic access to public sector information contribute to the democratic process and citizen participation, and to encourage the industry to develop new products and services based on government information⁴. Of particular relevance to this study, the document argues that *basic information* in a democratic constitutional state should be open and (electronically) accessible to all. Basic information comprises laws and regulations, court decisions and parliamentary records⁵. This position was confirmed in a later policy paper that also addressed access to administrative data and register data (e.g. cadastral, companies)⁶.

2 Systems of Access to Legal Information

As a consequence of the above policy, the central government started to develop web portals to provide access to organisational, policy and legal information at a single stop. The purpose was to make all information on governmental organisations accessible to the public at large. The underlying rationale at the time was one focussed on good democratic governance, while facilitating (commercial) re-use was a secondary objective. Currently, the portal www.overheid.nl gives access to full legislative texts and offers links to all current consolidated legislation at EU level and national level (wetten.overheid.nl or wetten.nl), as well as to the official publication versions and parliamentary records.

⁴ On a minor note, given the comparative purpose of these case studies, it might be worth noting that, already at the time, the UK website was considered *best in class* – and we presume, therefore, that it influenced the legal open data debate in the Netherlands.

⁵ Regarding case law, it argues that decisions of particular importance for understanding the law should be published by the government itself. Access to administrative information is predominantly regulated by the *Wet openbaarheid van bestuur* (Wob). Finally, the document also tackles the issue of executive agencies and other government entities such as the Kadaster (the Cadaster), the CBS (National Statistics Office, *Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek*) or the KNMI (Royal Meteorological Institute, *Koninklijk Nederlands Meteorologisch Instituut*). These were allowed to carry out certain market activities under strict conditions (e.g. no cross subsidies with public tasks).

⁶ Memorandum presented to the Lower Chamber of the Dutch Parliament by the Minister for Urban Policy and Integration of Ethnic Minorities, '*Towards optimum availability of public sector information*' (*The Hague, April 2000, Lower Chamber, session year 1999-2000, 26 387, nr 7*).

2.1 Access to legislation and official publications

In the course of the 1980s, the Dutch central government decided to outsource the creation of a consolidated databases with law and regulation to a consortium led by Kluwer. Departments of central government were guaranteed access under the contract. However, the consortium had also undertaken to exploit their product, a database called ADW (*Algemene Databank Wet- en Regelgeving*), at their own risk and expense, serving the wider public sector but also companies and individuals at ‘market’ prices. The consortium retained the database IP rights in the collection, a controversial move⁷. Following the new access policy, as soon as the contract with Kluwer expired in 2000, a new deal was struck. The maintenance and consolidation of amendments was outsourced. The legislation database became freely accessible to everyone on the internet.

Today, www.wetten.nl has *consolidated* legislation going back to 2002⁸. The maintenance of the legislation database is currently performed by SDU, on the back a public tender. It is, in fact, this database that also forms the basic element of the SDU commercial portals (OpMaat, Rechtsorde) and it is also one of SDU’s selling points: the legislation database product can be offered for free. It is worth noting, for the sake of clarity, that the publication is offered in two different layers: wetten.overheid.nl responds to the needs to make the data user-friendly. The Open Data layer itself can be found at www.data.overheid.nl/data/dataset/basis-wettenbestand. Here, the *BasisWettenBestand*, the raw data, can be downloaded in bulk for future (re) use⁹.

In the meantime, Kluwer continues to produce and maintain its own legislation database as the company believes it has at least as many functionalities as the one produced by the government (and maintained by SDU)¹⁰. By doing so it also retains the know-how and the product to be able to compete again in future public tenders.

2.1.1 Other Official Publications & Parliamentary Proceedings

As with Kluwer, it was also the former State printer, SDU, already privatised, that, further to the existing framework agreement regarding the publication of the official state bulletins, was also responsible for publishing parliamentary records (*kamerstukken, handelingen en officiële publicaties*) from 1995 onwards. These platforms ran in parallel to the information offered, in part, by the parliamentary website and later, since 1999, by overheid.nl¹¹. In July 2009, the Electronic Publications Act (*Wet Elektronische Bekendmaking*) was enacted in the Netherlands. The law made electronic (pdf) versions of official publications the authentic versions. Centralised access to legal information under the new framework of www.officielebekendmakingen.nl is now as follows:

⁷See M van Eechoud, ‘Openbaarheid, exclusiviteit en markt: commercialisering van overheidsinformatie’, *Mediaforum* 1998-6, p 177-184.

⁸ Unconsolidated legislation goes back much longer.

⁹ P Bartelings, M van der Kaaij en J Soeters, Open Access in de juridische praktijk, 16 December 2013.

¹⁰ Source: interview with Wolters Kluwer, May 2015.

¹¹ When overheid.nl was first launched in 1999 it still did not contain legislation, which was still under exclusive agreement of the Kluwer consortium.

Structure Dutch Official Publications website

Officiële bekendmakingen, www.officielebekendmakingen.nl (part of www.overheid.nl)				
	<i>Staatsblad</i>	<i>Staatscourant</i>	<i>Tractatenblad</i>	Parliamentary Proceedings
Organ	Min. Justice, published by SDU	Min. Interior	Min. Exterior	Parliament
Content	Official Bulletin, laws, decrees, regulation (as per constitutional obligation)	Gouvernement Bulletin', resolutions from the cabinet of ministers etc...	International agreements, decisions	Parliamentary Proceedings
Digital availability	Texts since 1995	Texts since 1995 (only partly available before 2009)	Texts since 1951	Texts since 1995.
Official (authentic) version	Digital (.pdf version), since 2009 Print, before 2009	Digital (.pdf version), since 2009 Print, before 2009	Digital (.pdf version), since 2009 Print, before 2009	Digital (.pdf version), since 2009 Print, before 2009
Available formats	Digital only: .pdf, .odt, .xml	Digital only: .pdf, .odt, .xml	Digital only: .pdf, .odt, .xml	Digital only: .pdf and .xml
Outside www.officielebekendmakingen.nl	---	---	---	- Texts 1814-1995 to be found in www.statengeneraaldigitaal.nl . Available under PDF or text - Pre-official and draft texts since 1995 also available at the websites of the individual chambers: www.eerstekamer.nl , www.tweedekamer.nl

Since 2013, some local and regional bodies have also decided to make their official bulletins (*Gemeentebleden, Provinciale bladen, Waterschapsbladen*) available through this (central) site¹².

Today, a special unit working for the Ministry of the Interior is responsible for these publications. KOOP (Knowledge Centre for Official Government Publications) was set up with the mission to transition the official journals *Staatscourant, Staatsblad* and *Tractatenblad* to digital authentic versions and to enhance their visibility on the internet. It is now the body responsible for the upkeep of a consistent and standard procedure in the electronic publishing of official documents. KOOP works closely with SDU in this process.

2.1.2 Access to case law

In the Netherlands, courts have an important role in shaping the law, especially with respect to open norms and any ‘gap-filling’. As elsewhere, to correctly understand statutory law also requires access to its interpretative case law. Case law publishing has traditionally been a commercial endeavour¹³. Since the 19th century, Kluwer, SDU but also smaller publishers, have published a variety of case law periodicals, catering to the judiciary, public administrations, law firms, to universities, etc. They had the workforce and financial means to support the process of production and distribution of such products, as well as a network of contacts within the court system.

¹² Local and regional bodies have an obligation to publish their *consolidated* regulation as per the central government’s publishing infrastructure of [overheid.nl](http://www.overheid.nl) (*Central Voorziening Decentrale Regelgeving*).

¹³ The principles laid out by article 121 of the Dutch Constitution (that courts sit in public and decisions are given in public) and article 6 of the European Convention of Human Right (on due process) were not considered to mandate active publication of all court decisions by government or courtsystem.

The website *www.rechstpraak.nl*, launched in 1999, was the result of the different projects undertaken by the government to create a nationwide intranet and make judicial cases available across courts and the government in a consistent manner under a single interface¹⁴. The public website was also triggered by the 1997 Cabinet document that identified the need to develop the internal *Justex* database into an electronic database freely accessible to all citizens. As part of this process, a universal case law identifier named ‘LJN’ was introduced. It has since been replaced by ECLI, described below.

Today, the database is the official source for Dutch case law, and is maintained by the Council for the Judiciary¹⁵. *Rechtspraak.nl* is a portal with metadata on about 1.7 million decisions and full text for about 300k cases. The database continues to grow by some 30,000 cases annually¹⁶. Open data is a web service available for both retrieval of the documents themselves (court decisions) and / or (ECLI) metadata in XML format.

Only a selection of decisions is published. Dutch constitutional law dictates that court hearings are conducted and decisions given in public. There is however no general law that mandates publication of the text of (every and all) court decisions. The Council has developed objective criteria to aid decision making on publication (legal or societal relevance outside the boundaries of the dispute decided being one key factor)¹⁷ and meet the requirements of data protection law (i.e. anonymization policy). Of the decisions published, almost 50% come from the criminal court/court of appeal and around 35% from civil law courts (family law excluded).

3 Actors

In the section above, we have explained how the public sector has created a legal environment conducive to private initiatives to meet customers’ needs, especially after 2000,

¹⁴ The unit tasked with the mission was a division of the Council for the Judiciary (*Raad van de Rechtspraak*) called BISTRO (*Bureau voor Internet applicaties en toepassingen voer rechterlijke organisatie*), BISTRO merged in 2011 with the IT organisation of the Judicial Organisation (ICTRO) to become Spir-it, the ICT company for the Judiciary. See also Prof.mr. H. Franken et al, *Recht en Computer* (5th Ed, 2004, Kluwer, Deventer) 602.

¹⁵ The Council was established in 2002, as part of a policy aimed at improving the independent management of the court system (limiting the powers of the Minister of Justice).

¹⁶ 2010, Mommers and Zwenne. See also *Jaarverslag 2014 De Rechsprak*. In 2014, there were almost 1.8m court cases in the Netherlands.

¹⁷ The 2012 Selection criteria of the Council for the Judiciary are based on the Recommendation of the Committee of Ministers of the Council of Europe from 1995. See <https://www.rechtspraak.nl/Uitspraken-en-nieuws/Uitspraken/Paginas/Selectiecriteria.aspx> for full criteria. Most important criteria are: 1st: All the case law of the highest courts (4) and some other specific chambers has to be published unless they very obviously are irrelevant (e.g. cases having been rejected for formal reasons); 2nd: Cases with specific legal features. E.g. those involving preliminary questions to Court of Justice or some other specific procedures; 3rd: All Criminal cases where the defendant has been convicted to prison of four or more years; 4th: Those cases that have drawn media attention or have been discussed in legal literature; 5th: All other cases, as much as possible.

when the Dutch government decided to open up substantial datasets of legal information to the public at large.

In the context of this study, it is important to distinguish the actor as a creator of information and the actor as a consumer of information. Sometimes both come together, a common argument used by Open Access advocates to argue for author-pays pricing models. In this section, we will focus largely on the first category, that of the *actor as a publisher*, leaving production and consumption to the Method and Practice section.

In the Netherlands, legal publishers typically register with the National Publishers' Association (NUV). There are, currently, approximately 45 members registered with the Trade-related and Scientific Media (*Media voor Vak en Wetenschap*) section within the NUV¹⁸. Only a small proportion, however, focus on the legal profession or legal content. Some other legal publishers might not be registered with the association. This study focusses on a representative cross-section, in terms of revenues or representative of specific sectors or business models. With many of these we have also conducted interviews. For the sake of accuracy, it is also important to note that products such as online directories or trade magazines are also classified in many industry studies as professional publishing. This would raise the relevance of names such as IDG Netherlands and Springer in our study¹⁹. There are, in short, different criteria applied to the definition of professional publishing (or B2B publishing) which makes it difficult to define and quantify the Dutch legal information market as such²⁰.

3.1 The Dutch Market

Both academic and professional publishing, or business-to-business publishing, are very different markets from that of consumer publishing (general public). Traditional publishing for the general public has suffered the most during the current crisis, due to decreasing advertising income and consumer spending. One of the reasons professional publishing has proved more resilient is that demand is far more inelastic than in consumer publishing and bears lower correlation with the economic cycle. Another important difference is that authors publishing in academic (scientific) journals are generally not paid for their contribution, contrary to the authors in traditional consumer publishing. Reward is measured rather in

¹⁸ Membership of the legal publishers of the Dutch national publishers association (status as of 1 Dec. 2015) can be found here: <http://www.mvw.nuv.nl/ledeninformatie/ledenlijst.37066.lynkx>

¹⁹ Though Springer books does publisher legal books. See below, We will take, as a starting point, the definition drafted by PwC in a recent study on the Dutch professional publishing market. PwC defines the Business to Business (B2B) publishing market as 'the sale to business professionals and companies of business information, print and online directory advertising, print advertising in trade magazines, advertising on trade magazine websites, and trade magazine circulation spending. It also includes spending on print and electronic professional books'. Also PWC classifies business information into financial, marketing and *industry information*. The latter contains data and content focused on categories such as the law.

²⁰ PwC, The future of B2B publishing. Other sources speak of global professional publishing which is broken down into the core publishing activities—Books, Journals, Newsletters and *Looseleafs*, Databases and Directories, Online Services and Abstracting & Indexing—in the individual segments of Medical, Scientific, Legal and Business.

terms of intangible assets, such as reputation and recognition, and these are impacted by where academic authors publish, increasingly in international peer reviewed journals.

In the Netherlands, digitisation has caused a structural shift in the publishing industry by changing the cost base (fewer fixed costs, higher IT costs etc.) and, possibly as a result, allowing competitors to dominant legal publishers, such as Kluwer, to crop up and be, arguably, in a position to compete. In turn, as a defensive move, Kluwer, as Elsevier, is opening up new lines of business in software and services.

The Dutch market for legal publishing has been relatively stable in recent years, even though it has had to respond and adapt to the challenging economic conditions that have impacted law firms and academia, leading to a more selective approach to acquiring legal content, an overall pressure on pricing, from both the private and public sectors, and the growth of specialised law firms²¹.

Examples of major and smaller legal publishers in the Netherlands				
Publisher	Ownership	Type	Operating divisions/ Revenue	Business Model
	Est. 1836. Wolters Kluwer NL is part of Wolters Kluwer group, present in >150 countries. Stock exchange listed (market cap May'14: Eur 8,700m)	Largest online publisher Market leader in legal, regulatory, tax, accounting. Full product range: books, journals, online databases, tools, software, services	Total of Eur 3660m (2014), of which circa. 40% from Legal & Regulatory division. Services IT and Software 30%, solutions 70% (information systems such as Navigator)	Group revenue: approx 80% of total from Digital (68%) and Services (12%). Print formats fell by 9% y.o.y., to represent 20% of total vs 23% in 2013. 76% is recurring (subscription) revenue. Operating margin stood at 20.3% down from 21.5% in 2013. ²²

²¹ Wolters Kluwer, Legal & Regulatory Investor Seminar, 10 June 2014.

²² We have only some data for the Netherlands, it is not consistent and dates from 2013. For example, digital content and software revenue has almost doubled in the period 2009-2013 to reach 60%. Print saw, in the same period a decrease of 55% to 35%. Recurring revenue also increased in the period, from 72% to 77%. Most of the Kluwer portfolio in the Netherlands (approx. 90%) is focused on legal, tax & accounting.

	<p>Est. 1814 state owned printers. Privatized 1988 Bought by French int'l publisher Lefebvre Sarrut (ELS) 2013</p>	<p>Legal & Tax Focus on professional (not academic). Market leader in labour & company law</p>	<p>Total revenue figure: N/A</p> <p>Approx. 55% revenue from government (central/local). Main source of income online content subscription-based (e.g. OpMaat).</p> <p>Share books only 1-2% of total revenue.</p>	<p>Traditional book publishing (series), online legal databases (opMaat) and owner of Rechtsorde.</p> <p>SDU journals work on the basis of a pre-established format (i.e. combining elements of jurisprudence, articles, overviews of current topics etc), replicated across the different legal fields. SDU pays journal authors</p>
	<p>Est. 1998 (Boom group est. 1841) Private, commercial</p>	<p>Legal Professional (academia/scientific approach)</p> <p>Books</p>	<p>Total revenue N/A Main source book publishing (50% of the revenue). Other: journal publishing and 'digital projects'. Journals: 20% are paper only, 80% digital or mix</p>	<p>Traditional book publishing, board decides on list. No paid authors (no copyright transfers either). Reputation of journals draws authors. Initiatives in OA</p>
	<p>2013 merger of platforms IEPT (2007) and Boek 9 (2004), Private, B.V. runs it, editorial responsibility. Web-based community: contributes / co-authors</p>	<p>Specialist lawyers (intellectual property). Web-based. Focus on IP news items (incl. legislation, cases). Cases crowd sourced (litigating attorneys mostly)</p>	<p>Total revenue figure: N/A. Its strength is low barriers to entry for authors/contributors and timeliness (cases published within days of being handed down).</p>	<p>Freemium. Initially funded only through sponsorship and (job) advertising. Growth meant rise in editing & hosting costs prompted change of business model. Since January 2015 pay-wall for a significant part of its content Eur 120 p.a., per user (also group rates).</p>

ArsAequi	Est. 1951 Non-profit foundation	Primary customer group: law students. Print and digital	Total revenue figure: N/A Net income: <50k	Journal, cases and materials for law students. Book publishing, (legislation, case law compendia). Case law books with case notes written by (unpaid) authors, generally academics. Also, monthly subscription magazine.
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3.2 Content Integration Systems

Fairly recent entrants in the value chain are content integrators. In essence these companies are legal search engines that help users access legal content from a wide range of publishers. Content includes that which is freely released by the public sector, e.g. under www.overheid.nl, and commercial sources to which the customer is subscribed (Kluwer, SDU, etc). Their added value resides, therefore, not so much in the content, which they don't generally licence themselves, but in the layout of their interface, the strength and accuracy of their search engine and their user-friendly functionalities.

3.2.1 Providers of Content Integration Systems

Rechtsorde and *Legal Intelligence* are the major competing service providers. Each offers the user the possibility to search different legal sources, both public and private, under a single interface. They are, in essence, dedicated search engines with information management tools. Both companies give access to a very similar range of content and user functionalities.

The value chain of content integration

Three party construction: the value chain of content integration

Rechtsorde and Legal Intelligence access both public content as well 'closed' commercial content, as long as the end user has a licence agreement in place with the relevant commercial provider. Generally, the content behind the interface of Rechtsorde or Legal Intelligence is contracted directly with the

publisher. That is, publishers do not allow Rechtsorde or Legal Intelligence to contract content directly with their user/subscriber (although some smaller publishers or content in lower demand might be licenced directly to Rechtsorde/Legal Intelligence). These integrators generally receive a list of individual publications that they have to provide access to (except for universities, which work under a different model). It is also common that law

firms ask to have their own internal ‘know-how’ databases (which include templates and generally ‘best practice’ examples) and their internet library connected to the content integrator (e.g. appearing as results to specific searches). These are so-called *data delivery services*, often requested in the context of information management of law firms. Generally, the price for the basic functionality is based on the number of fee-earners in a law firm and agreements are closed for an average of 3 years, with annual payments.

A remarkable issue, and one that indicates where the market is going, is that both, originally independent companies, have been acquired in recent years by large publishing houses in the Netherlands. Wolters Kluwer acquired Legal Intelligence (2011), and Rechtsorde became a SDU group company (2012). Both companies remain operationally separate from their parent companies. Further, the CRM systems are kept behind Chinese Walls, so that none of the companies will have access to the CRM and general usage data (information on searches, trends and other vital information when developing new products) of their respective content integrators. Under the current construction, the latter require backend access to the subscribed materials. The value of the usage data is significant and Legal Intelligence often conducts research on this usage, for quality improvement and in consultation with their customers.

4 Methods

In this section we aim to discuss the methods whereby legal information is made available in the Netherlands, examining both the legal and business models in place.

4.1 Methods for publishing legal information: Public Sector

The publication of legislation, case law and other official publications is publicly funded to the extent this is viewed as a public task. As regards case law, though, the question of what case law should indeed be published, remains controversial. Increasingly, though, the debate is focusing on the quality of publication (i.e. how far should the public sector go in terms of accessibility) and whether the publication of literature and commentary is something the public sector should play a role in.

4.1.1 Issues with the publication of case law.

Regardless of the *status quo*, by which a fair number of Dutch cases are published under clear selection criteria, we could certainly think of reasons to publish more case law, especially that from district courts. The key here is that, in some procedures, only those decisions which are legally interesting are published (that is, the ‘deviations’) rather than those with standard reasoning. As such, the court cases that are published might not do much towards the *understanding* of the law, given that they are not good examples of what normally happens in the vast majority of cases, which is precisely what would be interesting to most lawyers when assessing the courts’ interpretation criteria.

Publishing more case law, however, would be only be a viable option if anonymization becomes a less costly process,. Also, it may be argued that the search interface of

rechspraak.nl should enable the user to distinguish ‘routine’ from ‘interesting’, so (s)he will not be flooded with irrelevant results. Of course, intermediaries could also deal with this issue. In any case, the underlying question remains how good anonymisation currently is, given it remains relatively easy to re-identify parties (e.g. often just a few queries on Google can suffice). In that sense, any decision to open up all decisions on the internet (i.e. accessible world-wide, for ever, on the back of the public interest) would need to be balanced against the privacy interests of parties, and public interest in limiting public spending.

On the subject of simplifying the anonymisation process it is largely done manually, although experiments with anonymisation software take place. Further, the Council of the Judiciary has to respect the autonomy of the courts, it is not just an administrative matter, and this reflects on the inherent tension between autonomy and standardised working procedures.

Of course, any publication strategy which involves selection is open to criticism. In that sense, the approach taken by the Netherlands is defensible on the back of its (i) elaborate selection criteria, possibly best in class in the EU and (ii) reliance on judges and clerks to decide on the importance of the case at hand.

4.1.2 Licensing and IP

At the time of the launch of *overheid.nl* it was decided to use, as the default copyright policy, the so-called Creative Commons Zero (CC0) public domain dedication to texts on the portal. By applying such a licence, the Government surrenders any copyright that might exist in the content. The use of the CC model presupposes there is copyright in the licensed information to start with, which in the Netherlands is not the case for laws and other regulations, or for court decisions and administrative decisions²³. Further, certain Creative Commons licenses are at odds with the principles underlying freedom for information law (right to access official documents) as well as with requirements of the Directive 2013/37/EU on re-use of public sector information (‘PSI Directive’)²⁴, e.g. share-alike provisions.

²³ Rijksoverheid.nl is the first government site to make content available under CC0, which means that the content as public domain status is granted. The government thus provides a signal that it is serious about the open sharing of (public) information." — Martin Arnold, CC Netherlands (<http://creativecommons.nl/2010/03/31/rijksoverheid-in-het-publieke-domein/>). See M van Eechoud and B van der Wal, ‘Creative Commons Licensing for public Sector Information. Opportunities and Pitfall’, IViR, January 2008; M. van Eechoud, ‘Friends or Foes? Creative Commons, Freedom of Information Law and the EU Framework for Re-Use of Public Sector Information’ in L. Guibault (ed.), *Open Content Licensing: From Theory to Practice*. Amsterdam: Amsterdam University Press 2011.

²⁴ The use of *share-alike* clauses by public sector bodies can be at odds with the requirement of both freedom of information law and the law on re use of PSI, see M van Eechoud 2011.

4.1.3 Unique Legal Identifiers in the Netherlands.

ECLI

The case law of the EU courts is of great significance to the legal professions in EU member states. It is also commonly accepted that case law of other EU member states is important. In that sense, it stands to reason that there is a market for pan-European case law services, but these have not fully developed because of accessibility and language barriers. The EU is active in the promotion of cross-border initiatives in the field of uniform identifiers. The flow of legal information can be aided adopting the European Case Law Identifier (ECLI) as well as a minimum set of uniform metadata. In the Netherlands, the ECLI identifier has been implemented throughout the judiciary, from the *Hoge Raad* (Supreme Court) to districts courts. The Council for the Judiciary coordinates ECLI. It was introduced in June 2013 and replaces the former country case number (LJN)²⁵. ECLI should make it easier for distributed commentary and content integration services to develop over the coming years: legal information and improved search capabilities are likely to play a key role in this respect²⁶.

JuDoReg

JuDoReg is a work in progress. It is, essentially, a digital object identifier (DOI), alike to the ISBN. It is being developed by the so-called Juriconnect group, and an off shoot of a standardization effort by the tax authorities. The group serves as a platform for the exchange and standardisation in the legal field. Its members includes sources, providers and users of legal information from government, industry and academia.²⁷ The JuDoReg DOI would uniquely identify all legal articles published in the Netherlands, whether authored by academics or professionals. This can help organise and structure the content available in the various university repositories, e.g. facilitating cross-repository search and strengthening open acces.

²⁵ For reasons of continuity and consistency, the LJN number is now part of ECLI. Rechtpraak.nl publishes all Dutch ECLIs, together with at a minimum decision characteristics: rendering court, date, case number. Where known, publication references are also given for any reports of the decision in journals or databases.

²⁶ E.g. the MARC model (Model for Automated Rating of Case Law), makes it possible to rate the importance of a particular statement on the basis of ‘legal authority’ In the words of its author (Marc van Opijnen, a KOOP employee): ‘*MARC does not try to establish the uniqueness of single decisions by trying to understand the legal reasoning, but instead uses the wisdom and opinion of the legal crowd to establish whether a decision will play a role in future legal practice and debate*’.

²⁷ Juriconnect member are i.a. Ministry of Interior, the Ministry of Justice, SDU, Kluwer, the University of Amsterdam, Stipp (a consultant and provider of information processing services) and Reed Business Information. See www.juriconnect.nl.

4.1.4 LIDO

The institutionalisation of KOOP as the office responsible for (digital) access to legal databases and for the Open Data Portal of the government seems to have prompted a more active role of government in publishing (raw) legal information.

KOOP, as our interviewee explains, recognizes that there are different steps to be taken to arrive at maximal accessibility. First, the legal data has to be available (preferably in an open format with no re-use restriction). This has, arguably, proved to be a success in the Netherlands, at least regarding legislation, official publications and case law. Secondly, the data needs to be structured. For this purpose, several initiatives are underway in the Netherlands. One is the implementation of the ECLI identifier described above. Third, the structured data needs to be linked.

LIDO is a linked open data project aiming to combine the existing legal open data (legislation and case law) and literature²⁸. Literature would be delivered under the POC initiative (*freely accessible*) or as links to commercial literature (*paid for*). The government is currently in talks for commercial publishers and law firms to reach an agreement.

4.1.5 Contracts with the private sector

Law, regulations and court decisions are primary outputs of public authorities and we have seen that, today, information in electronic form is managed mostly in centralized systems, used across government, legislature and courts. Public authorities however not only consume their ‘own product’, they also require access to added-value legal information, e.g. academic literature, case comments, professional information. This is increasingly contracted centrally, by the Ministry of Finance rather than by each court individually²⁹. The exact scope of the contract varies, though, as each tender specifies the independent executive agencies involved (*zelfstandige bestuursorganen* or ‘ZBO’), provincial organs etc.

As an example, already mentioned earlier, SDU holds contracts with the government (some regarding public electronic publications -*openbaar elektronische publicaties*-, *wetten.nl* etc) on the basis of public tenders. Regarding content integration systems, Legal Intelligence won the last (*best value*-based) procurement tender and supplies the central government (*Rijksoverheid*), courts and tax authorities, among others. Again, they only wanted existing parties to participate in the tender (which automatically reduced the number of competitors to two, Legal Intelligence and Rechtsorde). The list of government entities served is, as we explained above, based on the list provided in the tender and depends on several factors (e.g. some ZBOs are served depending on the degree of control exercised by the central government, etc).

²⁸ This initiative would be done in a manner consistent with the framework of the EU Directive 2013/37/EU amending Directive 2003/98/EC on the re-use of public sector information.

²⁹ The contract is usually for 3 years. Given that the payment is all-inclusive, the government is increasingly taken a harder stance when it comes to paying for freely available information.

4.2 Methods for publishing legal information: Commercial publishers

4.2.1 Traditional business models and sources of revenue

As we already foregrounded in the Actors section, the development of commercial legal publishing has not been much different to that of the publishing industry at large. Publishers have had to adapt the pricing models in the shift of print to digital. The main challenge has been to create a value proposition that users are willing to pay for. Digital publishing vastly reduces the costs of distribution compared to what they used to be. This increased availability of open legal data makes it attractive for new players to enter the market, and, as result, pressure to provide value added increases. Finally, more than ever before, the battle for the user is not only fought as regards the content itself but also as regards enrichment tools such as search, linking and integration. As a result, new players have entered the market to engage in these digital service provision roles, such as content integrators.

Traditional commercial publishers rely on different sources of revenue (i) circulation income (pay per copy) (ii) advertising-based income (including sponsoring) and (iii) subscription income. In the legal information market, however, subscription remains the dominant method with some advertising added into the mix, as supplementary source of revenue. In that sense, the legal publishing market has proven to be quite resilient to change. Spending on legal information is not seen as discretionary, it concerns ‘*must-have*’ content, for which there is low price elasticity of demand.

Commercial publishers do recognize that the public sector in the Netherlands has a certain responsibility to make public legal information available and the public task mandates the general open access nature of wetten.nl and rechtspraak.nl. That is, publishers might agree that the government should publish data ‘as is’ (raw data), but they also believe that government should not engage in value adding as this is seen as the domain of private sector parties, in line with the principles of the PSI Directive³⁰. There is a certain tension between the public administration’s responsibility to inform citizens adequately, and the role of publishers. The latter argue that it’s precisely the low consumer-friendliness of ‘raw’ legal texts that gives opportunities to the private sector. Companies like *Ars Aequi* or *Boom* have, in recent years, traditionally endeavoured to provide abstracts of cases and, generally, have edited collections targeted at different groups or specialised areas of the law³¹. Similarly, the offer of parliamentary history and the evolution of a particular piece of legislation is also something that *Boom* believes meets users’ needs given that it provides integration.

4.2.2 Open Access

Boom is active in OA and *Kluwer* is also already offering the Green OA to its authors. One of the main challenges to the uptake of the Gold OA model is, apart from the obvious financial implications of moving from a subscription-based, user- pays system to an author-pays system, the lack of apparent transparency in setting the so-called article processing

³⁰ LIDO would, however, suggest otherwise

³¹ It is worth noting, though, the specific characteristics of the *Ars Aequi* user group. Law students are particular in their behaviour, often making these abstracts available online without any clearance of copyright licenses

charges (APCs) in an otherwise transparent Dutch legal publishing market. Further, while APCs might be prove prohibitive for some authors, other parties might see not considered price to be as relevant as the stand and reach of a particular journal. Nevertheless, publishers also agree that the Dutch legal information market is probably too small a market to benefit from the existence of full OA journals and the language barrier hinders supranational interest

4.3 Methods for publishing legal information: Universities

4.3.1 Universities as producers: research and journals

In the Netherlands, all universities have a repository where research is made available under Open Access. For example, the University of Amsterdam has UvA-DARE, its Digital Academic Repository, which contains citations of publications by UvA staff. It harvests publications and other outputs that UvA academics have to report in a dedicated tool (called Metis)³². An increasing number of these publications (generally articles or PhD theses) are full-text available via the database.

In addition there is Narcis, the main national portal set up in 2004, which provides access to information on scientific research projects and their outputs, including those in (OA) university repositories but also other publicly-funded research institutes (e.g. NWO)³³, datasets from some data archives and metadata on research projects, researchers and research institutes. Publications are however incomplete, which could change if Narcis became fed through university research outputs registration systems. As of March 2015, Narcis includes over 1.1 million publications, some 40% of which are OA (including some 66k PhD theses and 165k articles)³⁴.

Some OA journals have been initiated by universities (e.g. Erasmus university law review, Utrecht law review, etc.) but these do not seem to take off: Tilburg law review was discontinued as the university decided to stop subsidizing. This illustrates that the transition from subscription based publishing to (electronic) OA is not easy.

An aspect that would require more clarity is the policy of universities regarding copyright ownership³⁵.

OAPEN is a Netherlands-based online library and publication platform, and a non-profit foundation dedicated to the OA publishing of academic books. At Dutch level, it builds on the OAPEN-NL project which was set up in order to gain experience with OA publishing of academic books. Initially, between 2011 and 2012, 50 academic books were published in the Netherlands under OA, with subsidy from the National Research Council (NWO). For every

³² Several universities used the same tool, but METIS is being phased out and replaced by several other tools

³³ NWO is the Dutch abbreviation for the Dutch Organisation for Scientific Research or National Research Council (Nederlandse Organisatie voor Wetenschappelijk Onderzoek).

³⁴ <http://www.openaccess.nl/news/481-400-000-open-access-publicaties-in-narcis> and narcis.nl website

³⁵ OA models and repositories require that copyright permissions are in order

OA title, the publishers provided a similar title that was published in the conventional way for comparison. The key conclusion of the initiative was that OA publishing has no negative effect on book sales whereas it increased online usage and discovery considerably. This, however, did not lead to increase of citations in the research timeframe³⁶. At the start of 2014, the OAPEN Library had 55 (international) publishers contributing 2,075 publications (where authors pay to cover the production costs).

4.4 New Initiatives

4.4.1 Dutch Open Access policy

Open Access is a hot topic at political level in the Netherlands, as it is in the European Commission, UK government and elsewhere. The Netherlands will hold the presidency of the EU during the first half of 2016, and in a letter to Parliament the Cabinet expressed its intention to promote open access to scientific publications and the use of research results³⁷. Previously, Sander Dekker, the Dutch State Secretary and British counterpart Greg Clarke, released a ‘non-paper’ titled ‘*Open Access to Publications and Data*’³⁸ which highlights the importance of open access in the creation of an European Research Area.

The Netherlands aims to have 60% of all Dutch government-funded publications under the OA regime by 2016 and 100% by the year 2024. Ultimately, the goal is to establish the Gold road of OA. Also, the National Science Foundation (NWO) which already favoured OA, is now moving to a policy where all research funded with their monies must be published OA (outputs and research data). A study commissioned by the Dutch Ministry of Education³⁹ concludes that the costs should not be expected to rise under OA. According to the study, the Netherlands publishes a total of ca. 42,000 scientific articles per year, half of which could be traced on the internet as OA in the following 10 years. This involves gold, green and hybrid forms of open access. The percentage of gold OA is estimated to be 12% (c. 5,000 Dutch articles)⁴⁰, 60% of which is estimated to have taken place under the ‘*author pays*’ model.

Of course, this is a very mixed bag. Legal articles represent a fraction of the total. In the scientific world, almost all research is conducted through public funding but in the law domain it is different: a lot of the contributions are made by legal professionals and not by academics. Learned societies have problems moving to OA because usually combined

³⁶ Please see Oapen.nl project description and OAPEN.org

³⁷ See also ‘*Resultaten van publiek gefinancierd onderzoek moeten dan ook publiek beschikbaar zijn*’ Tweede Kamer, vergaderjaar 2014–2015, 31 288, nr. 414 – January 2015

³⁸ <http://www.rijksoverheid.nl/documenten-en-publicaties/publicaties/2015/03/23/non-paper-open-access-to-publications-and-data.html>

³⁹ To reach that conclusion, Ecorys first estimated the total costs for article processing fees (APCs) if all academic content would be published as OA, at € 33 to € 50 million. The study estimates the amount that is currently paid by the total public market for the services of commercial publishers at € 45 million. The contracts closed between publishers and universities/*hogescholen* representatives (SURF market) in 2013 amounted to circa € 39 million. The public market (for these publishers) is however larger than this, given that some Dutch knowledge centres (e.g. RIVM, CPB) reach agreements individually with the (commercial) publishers

⁴⁰ The total number of article is calculated on the basis of scientific articles available in Scopus and Web of Science. Data for 2013.

membership of society plus subscription to journals, and moving to OA means you have to pry this apart, with uncertain outcome for membership numbers. Also, many journals have authors from legal practice (who are not used to OA and are suspicious of it – author can buy exposure). As a result, this complicates the envisaged OA policy which is expressly directed at scientific (academic) authors and journals.

All in all, while OA *content* is certainly important, we should not forget that providing good *search* capabilities is arguably the biggest challenge today. Indeed, the costs of indexing OA articles and journals are often underestimated and university repositories are becoming haystacks lacking in proper (and possibly expensive!) maintenance.

In addition, as we discussed earlier, legal professionals are frequently both academic and practising lawyers, or legal advisors and civil servants. The blurred boundaries of the legal professional makes it difficult to classify research as scientific or not - as long, of course, as we strictly equate ‘scientific’ with ‘academia’. OA policy at government level seems to presume that outputs are always academic writings resulting from scientific research. In many law journals, traditionally academic work has been published side by side with more practical/professional writings. An OA policy imposed for ‘academic’ works is therefore bound to produce difficult delineation issues and might force legal scholars to desert mixed journals, forgoing the ‘societal impact’ they are expected to have.

4.4.2 Open Access in new Dutch Copyright Law (update July 2015)

The Dutch Copyright Act has just been amended with a view to strengthening authors’ bargaining position⁴¹. It includes an unwaivable right of authors of academic short works to disseminate their work free of charge to the public, after the work has been published.⁴² To protect publisher’s interests, a reasonable embargo period applies. The parliamentary record contains little guidance on what constitutes a reasonable time, it seems the initiators of the amendment that resulted in the OA provision assumed that publishers and authors would come to an agreement on that in individual cases⁴³. The new Article 25.f.a. Dutch Copyright Act thus particularly facilitates Green OA (as Gold OA implies the first publication of the ‘official’ journal version is done under OA conditions). It only applies to academic short works (so not to e.g. monographies) that have been funded completely or largely with Dutch public funding. The NWO is a major funder. Dutch universities are also almost exclusively

⁴¹ *Wet Auteurscontractenrecht, Stb. 30 juni 2015, 257* (Parliamentary records: *Kamerstukken II 2011/12, 33308*). The revision is the result of a long process, which started with the 2004 IViR study on copyright contract law, commissioned by the Minister of Justice, see P.B. Hugenholtz, L. Guibault, *Auteurscontractenrecht, naar een wettelijke regeling? (Copyright contract law, towards statutory regulation?)*, Amsterdam: Institute for Information Law 2004 [available at www.ivir.nl]

⁴² For a short English introduction to the open access provision, see L. Guibault, ‘Back on the Green Road: How Imperative are Imperative Rules?’, *Kluwer Copyright Blog*, 19th April 2015.

⁴³ For a discussion see D. Visser, ‘De open access bepaling’, *AMI* 2015-3, p. 85 ff.

publicly funded (tuition fees are far below cost-price, and there is no culture of private sector funding through donations or endowments).

4.4.3 Stichting Platform Open Commentaren ('POC')

POC, an initiative which would fit in the larger LIDO project described above, is a peer production initiative of webbased legal commentary on legislation and caselaw.⁴⁴ Its initiators have been in talks with government officials about the possibility to have commentary from experts (academics, practising lawyers, etc) linked to the official websites for legislation, judicial decisions and those of general administrative bodies. The idea is that it is in the interest of public authorities to stimulate expert commentary to the public at large, as a good way to create a level playing field for legal advice in the Netherlands.⁴⁵ The project is expected to go live in the course of 2015.

The funding is expected to be provided by a number of law firms based in the Netherlands, both Dutch and international. The aim of POC is that in the long term the platform will offer a (partial) alternative to existing subscription packages offered by commercial publishers. Its prominent peer production social feature (revolving around speed and interaction) would be an advantage, but also its lower cost.

Some of the more obvious challenges faced by POC stem from the increasing competition among law firms. Giving away (valuable) information for free to all is regarded as a loss of know-how. This may put pressure on the number of firms willing to participate and on the resources they invest in shared initiatives like POC. Also, ways would have to be found to ensure the public/reader can distinguish public content from commercial information.

5 Practices: the Dutch legal market

We can observe a series of developments that have changed the manner in which users engage with legal information and which runs in parallel to general trends in the society at large, such as user generated content or OA.

5.1 Management of Legal Information

5.1.1 Universities

Universities/higher education institutions both produce legal information and are a large buyer from commercial publishers. They are increasingly reaching centralised deals through the VSNU, the association that represents the 14 Dutch universities. Open Access has become a core issue in the so-called '*big deals*', the all-in multidisciplinary packages universities buy from the largest commercial publishers (e.g. Elsevier, Kluwer, Springer). New deals should facilitate the transition towards open access academic publishing and reduce subscription

⁴⁴ <http://rechtcommentaar.nl>. It would use Creative Commons licensing.

⁴⁵ We have, nevertheless, been unable to gather any high-level government backing of this idea.

fees for university libraries⁴⁶. The VSNU has already closed a landmark deal with Springer and after tenuous negotiations⁴⁷ with Elsevier.⁴⁸ It is in negotiations with other publishers such as Wiley, Kluwer and Oxford University Press. The universities seek to prevent 'double dipping,' whereby they still pay subscriptions but must also pay APCs for open access in hybrid journals.

5.1.2 Law firms and Legal Professionals

In the Netherlands there are over 17,000 lawyers, a figure that has been rapidly increasing over the past years⁴⁹. There were also 8,465 law firms as of the start of Q2'15 (April 2015) up from 6,505 in the same period of 2010. Similarly, the number of legal counselling firms (*rechtskundige adviesbureaus*) has increased from 3,510 to 5,620 in that same period.

Widespread access to (digital) information has softened the asymmetries of old and the economic crisis has increased competition among law firms, putting pressure on the high hourly fees common in the boom years. New business propositions are required⁵⁰. Similarly, whereas they are likely to be eager to market themselves to businesses (though, for example, short case notes), they might not be so keen to share information with other firms.

In 2015, some Dutch law firms have decided to stop ordering physical books to focus exclusively on e-books, generally avoiding the payment of multiple licensing for simultaneous access by pushing for the 'one access at the time' policy. Of course, other models are available but law firms seem to try to stay away from the maximum number of simultaneous users or unlimited number of users price references. Further, some law firms are considering disposing of their physical books altogether and retain a low sample of paper copies in their private libraries (i.e. current issues of journals)⁵¹.

It is also common for large law firms to, as a matter of policy, subscribe to all available online resources. This would respond to a desire for completeness coupled with potential price discounts. Indeed most law firms have all-inclusive deals with the most relevant publishers

⁴⁶ The Association of Dutch Universities VSNU regularly reports on the issue on its website www.vsnu.nl (partly in English).

⁴⁷ <http://www.infodocket.com/2015/01/08/scholarly-publishing-dutch-universities-dig-in-for-long-fight-over-open-access-as-talks-with-elsevier-resume/>

⁴⁸ The VSNU and Elsevier reached an agreement in principle on open access and subscription that should kick off in 2016. Details are to be hammered out.

⁴⁹ 17,000 was the number as per 2012, the latest available. However, given the increase in the number of law firms we can safely assume that the number of lawyers has also gone up. See statistics at the CBS, <http://statline.cbs.nl/StatWeb/publication>

⁵⁰ Over the last few years, publications such as the Financial Times or the Economist have been commenting on the downward pressure of law firms' hourly rates and the competition among law firms, including new entrants (low value-added firms, in house law firms, accountancy firms etc). See <http://www.ft.com/intl/cms/s/0/9e0c2c74-ddeb-11e4-9d29-00144feab7de.html#axzz3ceN6N100>, <http://www.economist.com/news/business/21646741-lawyers-beware-accountants-are-coming-after-your-business-attack-bean-counters>, <http://www.economist.com/news/business/21594317-lawyers-biggest-customers-are-discovering-they-can-haggle-charging-more-getting-less>

⁵¹ Interview at Van Doorne, a Dutch law firm (February 2015). In fact, some universities in the Netherlands are also currently experimenting with the concept of a 'paperless university' where all publications for students are available digitally (e.g. University of Rotterdam).

(Kluwer, Boom, SDU, Elsevier, De Lex, Den Hollander, among others). These deals gives them access to all published material in the course of the year. In practice, this means access to all their online resources. In addition, some of these, eminently digital, resources are also produced in paper form, which Van Doorne, a Dutch law firm, sometimes also demands to have and which are already included in the deal.

Generally, because of its catalogue which covers virtually all areas of law and includes legislation and case law databases, Kluwer is the most widely used supplier and is still today regarded as ‘*must have*’ content (e.g. Kluwer Navigator is a staple as regards the usage of other search engines).

Also, the proliferation of smaller specialised firms in the Netherlands (notably in newer areas such as renewables, IT and tech law, etc.) means that the firm is not interested anymore in an all-inclusive package. Before, when buying Kluwer or SDU products, a law firm was also buying certainty. Today, there are specialised portals that deliver an arguably similar product, sometimes with a much quicker time-to-market, for a fraction of the price (e.g. Boek9, in the context of intellectual property law cases). Similarly, smaller and specialised firms means that alternative cases in other fields of the law are tackled on a case-by-case basis. In other words, firms are unlikely to buy full subscription packages for the ‘just-in-case scenario’. Rather, they would (like to) resort to a pay-per-use model. The large impact that this has on the cash flow generation of legal publishers (upfront and certain payments vs. cyclical) proves this is no easy decision for publishers.

5.1.3 Digital libraries

Digital libraries are generally successful as long as they grant access to an integrated collection of digital books. In other words, professionals and universities are generally not interested in negotiating for single e-books but to licence access to a collection of digital material (i.e. similar to a ‘*recht op toegang*’, or right of access). The lack of full integration is one of the reasons the adoption of OAPEN as a resource too is slower than would be expected otherwise.

Some of the Dutch publishers we have interviewed are wary of e-books because the market is moving to content integration, not to digital libraries comprised of ‘isolated’ items that the user cannot link together (e.g. through searching for a keyword throughout all books). The key aspiration of readers is to have multiple sources available as results of a query. For example, SDU is investing a lot in personalised digital services.

5.2 Law firms as authors

Authors employed at large law firms in the Netherlands generally retain copyright or sign up licences whereby articles published commercially (i.e. in the journals of legal publishers such as Kluwer) are also uploaded to the law firm’s website, in *.xml* or *.pdf* format, with hardly no embargo period. Generally, what the legal publisher would often demand in return is attribution. That is, that the source of the full article and/or the journal where the excerpt is published is quoted. Increasingly though, law firms negotiate retaining copyright in exchange

for keeping the original source on their website (i.e. *content marketing* for the likes of Kluwer and SDU, increasingly important for these publishers⁵²). Also, many authors are keen to assign, or exclusively licence, copyright, in exchange for royalties (i.e. heightened sense of belonging than charging a few upfront).

Lawyers are increasingly demanding as to where they publish. Often it is simply a matter of time, a cost-benefit analysis whereby a publishing in a blog or in a new journal is not worth the time invested. In other words, their reputation is improved when they write in the blogs of their own firms or for renowned journals. In that sense, there is a big pressure on publishing on specific terms. For example, the Erasmus Law school blog, published by the University of Rotterdam, has disappeared partly due to a lack of sufficient professional contributors to make it sustainable.

5.3 Community behaviour: alternative publishing and social networks

We have argued earlier on in the Context section that, one of problems with the publication of case law was the lengthy process incurred in by publishers (with turnover times of 10 months for an article on a particular ruling) and also the possibility of bias (always the same authors are hired or only the opinion of one party is published).

The proliferation of Web 2.0 should have led to a very different situation for the provision of legal information. The change of attitude is, nonetheless, not straightforward. Lawyers, and law students in particular, appear to be wary of writing for blogs and commenting articles. The reason lies perhaps in the high-end nature of some legal articles and how law students would appear risk-averse by nature and reluctant to provide opinions as a consequence. It might also be because they are aware of how difficult it is to erase comments in the digital domain and how future employers are scanning the web. It appears more informal networks such as Facebook are more successful in starting spontaneous debates, at least in some fields (e.g. Family law) but not in others (e.g. Immigration law). In short, generally speaking, law students in particular would appear to apply a high level of self-censorship making it hard for communities to emerge.

Though lawyers are wary of sharing information in many legal publications it would appear that practice-based, informal platforms are increasingly successful. The feeling of community is well developed about lawyers of a particular field. The *Vereniging Arbeidsrecht Advocaten Nederland (VAAN)*, as association of labour lawyers in the Netherlands are active have an online tool with specialised content. In the platforms there's also a chat tool that is only visible to members and seem to be a success, both in terms of networking as of information exchange. Publishers explain this as an urge to share, both among large and small firms, in order to raise the quality of lawyers.

⁵² Because, again, it provides references, links...it's hence, not so much about the content but about search visibility

There are also *niches*, such as sports law, which also feeds the community feel by having lawyers participate in publishing and annotating related case law through a popular LinkedIn group.

5.4 Re-assessing roles and service offerings

KOOP is, in essence, the government's own digital publishing house. It employs some 100 FTEs and offers specialized services in terms of digital search and legal informatics. In parallel, the role of the lawyer, and that of the traditional publisher, are changing. Some sources expect a decrease in the number of lawyers, currently 17,000 in the Netherlands, while the usage of artificial intelligence and big data will enable non-lawyers to deal with a high percentage of the legal information. As a result, publishers are now also looking to deliver legal information on different levels. That is, the publisher is starting to distinguish the more automated (non-added value) legal offering from the non-automated (value-added) work. Additionally, in doing so, publishers have also started to work on service offerings targeted at the non-lawyer. This might also require in the future an alternative way of processing legal information.

5.5 From subscription to alternative models

5.5.1 Open Access

As we have seen above, in academia there is pressure to move to open access, but also pressure for legal scholars to publish internationally. Publishers that have many practitioners in their author base seem to struggle to move towards open access. One example is Open Access Advocate (www.openaccessadvocate.nl) by Boom. The website hosts nearly 2,000 articles (as of 2015), generally written by legal practitioners. It also functions as a submission platform and gives access to OA articles from Boom's hybrid and OA journals. APCs are based on advocats hourly rates, and Creative Commons attribution licenses are used. Although it has a very reputable advisory board and is transparent on its review procedure (Boom has 5 double blind peer reviewed OA journals) and terms & conditions, uptake seems to be limited. According to our interviewees, possible factors are that the platform requires more time from professionals (submission, etc.) compared to traditional journals and that authors prefer longstanding journals with steady reputation.

One could argue that the lack of reputational interest, a big hindrance to a widespread uptake of OA journals would be overcome once the current system of (informal) journal ranking⁵³ among academics is replaced. Whether this can be realistically achieved is doubtful. The current system is valuable in that it works as an indicator of (academic) quality and allows for accountability. On the other hand, this means that the system also poses significant barriers to entry.

For the foreseeable future OA seems to be an add-on product to the existing plethora of subscription-based journals. It seems fair that commercial publishers need to experiment with

⁵³ Please note that in the law domain there is no *formal* ranking system as such.

new business model before they adopt more drastic policies. On the other hand, the current system would appear to only be affordable for large players who can cross-subsidize any loss-making OA initiative. Most publishers in the Netherlands do work with the Green Road OA model in some way or to some extent. Kluwer has a ‘*repository clause*’, SDU and Kluwer allow (almost simultaneous) postings on law firms’ websites, Ars Aequi has a month’s embargo before authors, mostly legal scholars (and some law students), can include their articles in *university* repositories. It is also worth noting that the level of uptake of OA is not equal in all fields of the law. In the fields of intellectual property, energy law or labour law, OA appears to command a larger degree of popularity⁵⁴.

5.5.2 From subscription models to ‘pay-per-use’ and ‘all you can eat’

Boom has a feature in Google whereby the user can search for journal articles directly. Once the user has found the article he or she was looking for, the user can pay for it individually, at Eur 9.90 without requiring a subscription⁵⁵. This model is also more prevalent in the sciences, rather than in the legal, field. We understand that most law publishers do not offer that possibility in the Netherlands (i.e. commercial publishers are mostly weary of cannibalisation of their journals).

The subscription only policy could be construed as a means to prevent cannibalisation of the journal format in which legal publishers are not interested. On the other hand, we could think of this model as one whereby the user receives what he wants ‘à la carte’⁵⁶.

SDU has received signs of interest regarding potential Spotify-like products. Boom also experiments with a streaming-based model. That is, the user can buy 24h access to a particular access without the need for subscription. In addition, Boom also has a streaming platform called *Tablr Legal*. Through this service, the user can read books and journals, both online and offline (cloud-based) for Eur 15 per month. This service is, however, not yet successful. Reasons may vary but given that most law firms already have Legal Intelligence or Rechtsorde, the level of available information is so high that even Eur 15 are not worth the hassle. Further, most of the Boom articles available under *Tablr Legal* are also accessible via these content integrators (if the law firm has a Boom subscription, of course). A last example of streaming is an initiative called **Jurify**, the brainchild of a legal management professional and a legal publisher. Jurify would provide access to all existing legal

⁵⁴ P Bartelings, M van der Kaaij en J Soeters, Open Access in de juridische praktijk, 16 December 2013

⁵⁵ For this purpose, Boom has an Index by Google contract and an additional contract with the so-called *Praktizijnsbibliotek* whereby Boom is allowed to use their website to refer articles to full journals? The library follows a search based on biblioeconomy techniques, based on links, not the content as such. It’s a bibliographical index.

⁵⁶ In line, with the successful business model in the music industry, pioneered by Apple’s iTunes, where music albums and CDs are ‘unpacked’ in such a way that the user can purchase individual songs instead of having to buy a whole album.

information in the Netherlands, both paid and free information, against a flat fee. What a sound pricing model is for streaming remains a thorny question.

6 Multiple device publishing

Whereas the legal profession generally responds to the *cliché* of the slow-adopter, traditional lawyer buried in mountains of paper⁵⁷, mobile internet appears to be the exception that proves the rule. Lawyers approve the widespread use of smartphones and tablets in the legal profession and internet applications (*apps*) geared to the search of legal content are popular⁵⁸. In the Netherlands, the active use of the mobile phone to access and consult legal information has also been noted by our interviewees. We have no actual data for the Dutch market but market leader Kluwer explains in its consolidated 2014 Annual Report that one of its business strategies is to *‘invest in mobile applications, cloud-based services, and integrated solutions’*.

Also, the Dutch public sector has been pursuing mobile platforms. Recently, KOOP launched *‘Wettenpocket’*, a free legislation *app* offering personalisation tools⁵⁹.

7 Outcome

It is clear that there are forces challenging the *status quo* of the current legal information market. New initiatives are being adopted, of which OpenLaws is one, and experts predict an upcoming paradigm shift. In that sense, for the informed observer, the Netherlands is possibly one of most interesting countries to analyse at this moment. It is a pioneer in the open (legal) data movement, enjoys a solid network of universities for a country its size, has a long-standing history of embracing professional publishing houses (e.g. Kluwer, Elsevier) who have started developing new business models, and has generally sophisticated users who are keen to experiment with new models (e.g. digital library licensing etc). Of course, high penetration of cable broadband and uptake of 4G mobile technology has vastly contributed to the digitalisation of legal information for the public at large.

Lastly, the Dutch government has played a fundamental role opening up legal resources in the early days of the internet and is today committed to the implementation of Open Access policies, especially for publicly-funded research. Further, it also supports Open Data policies for legal information. It will always be a challenge to delineate the role of the public sector – to safeguard access to law but also to foster innovation-- and that of commercial publishers.

⁵⁷ As experienced by most of the publishers we have interviewed.

⁵⁸ This is a trend observed by large publishers and confirmed by our interviewees. Reed Elsevier explains in its 2014 Annual Report the global increase in the use of Lexis Advance and lexis.com mobile content. In the US, penetration of mobile document access has been increasing at a rate of 143% year on year and a further 54% from 2013 to 2014.

⁵⁹ *Wettenpocket* apps consists of collections tailored to specific user groups or fields. Public administrations (units in departments, local authorities, etc.) can request to have a tailored one made. A pocket bundles information for a specific field or region: regulation, case law, links, parliamentary history, policy documents, etc. The user can even add notes. It uses existing open public sector data. ⁵⁹

Developments of the past years push commercial publishers to keep on adding value, rather than provide access to basic legal materials. Many professionals seem to rejoice at the prospect of raising bars in legal publishing as regards innovation, prompted by the public sector. However, an over-ambitious public sector might also impact the willingness of the private sector to develop new products.

On the ‘*production*’ side, traditional publishers have largely moved online but user paid content, rather than OA or advertising funded models are still dominant. Pricing structures are slowly changing (to e.g. pay per article etc.) however. Also, new entrants with a lower cost base and a quick *time to market* (e.g. community oriented, ‘*born-digital*’ services etc.) have some disruptive effect on incumbents in traditional legal publishing. The slow-paced changes paint the legal professional as someone reluctant to change acquired habits (fear of missing out, wariness in the provision of advice, competition...). In an increasingly competitive environment, where the internet eases the flow of information, lawyers seem very conscious of how the old adage that *information is power* holds up more than ever. On the one hand, they experiment with new business methods, at a time when artificial intelligence and big data are offering *El Dorado*, hoping to benefit from a first mover advantage (better adjusted client tariffs, more flexible outsourcing, efficient search etc). On the other hand, moving too fast, especially in a traditionally conservative industry, might be financially and reputationally counterproductive (contributing to underfunded and ‘untested’ OA journals etc.)⁶⁰.

The future will tell how initiatives and policies will actually change the legal information market in the Netherlands. To date, OA initiatives adopted by commercial publishers still lack mainstream adoption by authors and readers alike and we can only venture some of the reasons. Arguably, lack of visibility and user-friendliness might be the main cause OA publications are lagging behind, but it might also bear relation to the nature of the legal profession and, perhaps, to potentially underestimated costs of OA (i.e. it is a fact that the Gold model requires funding whereas the Green model is only an intermediary step in which the subscription model still prevails). An added difficulty is the delicate process of quantifying the socio-economic benefits of Open Data policies in the public sector, which complicates any cost and benefit analysis. We will see how the changes in copyright legislation that took place in July 2015 impact the development of OA in the Netherlands.

Of course, the mainstream adoption of OA initiatives could just simply be a matter of time. If we consider how the internet, a system essentially built to disintermediate communications and which was mass-adopted over 15 years ago, has indeed made a dent in legal publishers but not (yet) disqualified their business model, it could well be that the Netherlands needs at

⁶⁰ An example of how trends could be misunderstood is evidenced by the ‘free’ mantra. In professional publishing especially, it would appear that consumers are actually willing to pay if they perceive the added value: e.g. Kluwer closed down a niche accountancy periodical after advertising income dried up only to find out later that the small user base was actually a loyal one and had been willing to pay for the product if asked.

least another decade before it witnesses OA policies establishing a firm foothold in the country. Developments in scientific publishing are slower-than-expected.

An example. In 2002, when Wolters Kluwer sold their international scientific publishing division⁶¹ to venture capitalists, who later proceed it to merge it with their existing shareholding at *Springer Verlag* to form Springer Science+Business Media, the market was quoted describing the sale as ‘*a response to the threat posed by the increasing number of alternative journals being established by disaffected customers and the trend for researchers to self-archive their papers on the Web (...)*’. Those same words could also have been spoken today, some thirteen years later. It is, indeed, a slow process.

In any case, accessibility, whether open or otherwise, goes hand in hand with search, especially as the amount of (legal) information increases over time. Search intelligence and indexing are the key trends: big data doesn’t work if the data itself is not properly structured. In order to provide anything OA a good search engine is required. Therefore, given the technicalities and IT investment required to make such a move, it’ll be interesting to see how small players react to the challenge, and if consolidation triggered by the need for economies of scale becomes a *must*.

This case study is arguably one of the first analyses of the legal information market in the Netherlands. It shows there are important static elements, such as the continued presence of the same (large) players, but also that OA policies, the release of legal source material online by the government and the entry of new actors is creating dynamics in which Openlaws and similar initiatives have the potential to flourish.

⁶¹ Kluwer Academic Publishers (KAP) was a division of the Wolters Kluwer publishing group operating world-wide from offices in Dordrecht, Boston, New York, and London. Kluwer Academic Publishers comprised Kluwer Law International, Kluwer Academic/ Plenum Publishers, Kluwer Academic/ Human Sciences Press (journals only).

Annex I – Interviewees

[All interviews were conducted between January and May 2015. Please note that a large part of the report has been drafted on the basis of the appreciations made in the course of the below interviews. Therefore, the uses and methods provided, though they have been checked against the available literature and (scarce) statistical data, remains indicative and, to some extent, subjective].

Industry	Name	Surname	Institution	Other
<i>Academia/Doc</i>	Rosanne	van der Waal	Institute for Information Law, Documentation Centre	
<i>Academia/Doc</i>	Pascal	Braak	University of Amsterdam, Law Library	
<i>Academia/Doc</i>	Saskia	Woutersen-Windhouver	University of Amsterdam, University Library	
<i>Academia/Doc</i>	Marcel	Ottenbros	University of Amsterdam, University Library	
<i>Commercial/law firm</i>	Peter	Piepers	Van Doorne	Advisory Board Openlaws/Platform Open Commentaren (POC)
<i>Government/Administration</i>	Marc	van Opijnen	KOOP, Dutch Ministry of the Interior	Advisory Board Openlaws
<i>Commercial/Content Integration</i>	Laurens	Mommers	Legal Intelligence	
<i>Non Profit/Legal Publishing</i>	Janine	van Winden	ArsAequi	
<i>Commercial Publishing (large)</i>	Simon	van der Linde	Wolters Kluwer	
<i>Commercial Publishing (specialised/regional)</i>	Patrick	Blom	SdU	
<i>Commercial Publishing (specialised/regional)</i>	Wirt	Soetenhorst	Boom	
<i>Digital Publishing (specialised, IP)</i>	Dick	van Engelen	Boek9.nl	